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The Book

Daniel D., Hutto, *Beyond Physicalism*, (Advances in Consciousness Research), [John Benyamin's](#): Amsterdam/Philadelphia, 2000.

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Commentaries and replies

Marco Salucci, [Before Idealism](#) (with Hutton's reply)

Forums

Before Idealism

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One of the main attacks to physicalism mounted by Hutto derives from the classical argument of Nagel and Jackson: the knowledge argument. Hutto emphasizes an important feature of such an argument, a feature that is often underestimated by the literature about the subject. There is a physically inexplicable residual that comes from the fact that it is impossible to know what it is like to be a certain x because we would have to be that x . I agree that this is the problem posed to physicalism by the knowledge argument (as I have claimed in *Materialismo e funzionalismo nella filosofia della mente*, Pisa, ETS 1996), But I am more cautious than Hutto in drawing from it the antiphysicalist conclusion. The point of the knowledge argument is that different creatures cannot share mental states, but this point is not incompatible with identity theory. That mental states cannot be shared might be a banal consequence of the impossibility to share the brain states these mental states are identical to. Therefore, the question we have to ask is: does the fact that mental/brain states are not shareable imply that there is no explanation of how mental states originate, "emerge", "supervene" and so on from brain states or are identical with them?

I do not think so. The answer depends on what we mean by explanation. If in the future, neuroscience will show how mental states originate from brain states and *also* how some physical systems (brains) have the property to feel what it is like to be what they are, then, I think, this would be a fully satisfactory explanation (see my *Is consciousness a brain state?*, in << Iride >> May-August 2000, the [abstract](#) is available in this site).

Obviously the kind of explanation I am referring to is not available now. If it will be, only future science will provide it. However, the reference to future science leads us to another attack against physicalism devised by Hutto. Crane and Mellor proposed this type of criticism about ten years ago. They claimed that physicalism is either false, if it is based on the current science, or empty if it is based on future science. The first option is, obviously, a false target (although sometimes Hutto seems to take it seriously) because no physicalist ever claimed that present science is able to explain mental phenomena (behaviourism and the famous identification of pain with the excitation of C-fibers firing are obsolete proposals). As to the second option I must confess I do not understand it, because I cannot see the difference between asserting that << future science will find the cure for cancer>> and << future science will find the explanation for the origin of consciousness>>. Either they are both acceptable (this means: they are meaningful, not empty and not trivial, no matter if they will be stated as true or false) or they both can be rebutted. If somebody claims that consciousness makes the difference, we are clearly facing a question begging. It is already assumed, without argument, that consciousness cannot be a scientific object. Hutto's discussion about the Object-based Schema and the efforts to use space-time notions in order to grasp objectivity shows how difficult it is to have a definition for physical object, and therefore how badly founded physicalism is. But physicalists do not have to give a definition for physical object, since this is the task of science. The history of science, from seventeenth century mechanism to contemporary relativity and quantum mechanics, shows how the concept of physical object has changed according to science.

At this point, clarification is needed on the notion of physicalism. (Between the many possible definitions that I could quote, I wish to remember W. Sellars' quasi-Protagorean dictum: <<science is the measure of all things, of what is, and of what is not>>). A physicalist stance claims that (I limit the list to the points that count in the philosophy of mind): 1) physical is what physical science states as such; 2) empirical knowledge is necessary in order to assess how the physical world is; 3) if the mind is reducible to physical states, this can be decided only by empirical research; 4) if such a reduction is possible, this task is still up to an empirical research as is the kind of reduction available (and so is the choice between identity, emergence, supervenience and so on).

I am aware that Crane-Mellor-Hutto would easily criticize point 1: I can only repeat what I said above: surely it is not possible to charge physicalism with triviality, which is referring on the feature of continuous progress in scientific knowledge. To my view, the point 1 is important because it establishes a fundamental difference between the past materialism (e.g., Hobbes' one) and the contemporary one. Contemporary materialism does not involve any metaphysical thesis of its own, since it entrusts science with the task of stating the constituents of reality. Point 2 eliminates any *a priori* enquiry: valid information cannot be obtained without the contribution of experience (according to the Logical Positivist thesis:

<< synthetic a priori does not exist>>). Point 3 is an obvious consequence of what the founding fathers of identity theory (Place and Smart) thought the identity between brain and mental states to be: an empirical hypothesis. Therefore identity theory can be true or false: however, the settling of such a decision must be a scientific task. The demonstration a priori that identity theory is true or false has to be excluded. If we consider identity theory as an empirical hypothesis, then other consequence have to be considered: it is precisely the reason which the Place and Smart's physicalism is not empty, since it constitutes a legitimate and possible research program on which future investigations can be based. Finally, since there are many ways of reducing theories and also many ways of conceiving the mind-body relation (although remaining in a physicalist frame), I think the empirical research can carry out the same role in points 3 and 4.

Now we come to the issue of idealism, the metaphysical option Hutto defends and by which he means to exceed physicalism. Hutto claims that idealism (in particular Bradley's absolute idealism) is incompatible with physicalism but not incompatible with science. Therefore, we could exceed physicalism without abandoning natural science. Of course, it is necessary to agree on what science is. I believe that it is very difficult to imagine science without, at least, points 1 and 2. Therefore, exceeding physicalism means exceeding science too. I know very well that about the notion of idealism and its relationships with empirical science there are several unfounded commonplaces, most of them have been dissolved by Hutto's analysis. However we must consider the fact that the notion of idealism still has a series of meanings that have featured in idealistic doctrines. There is not a single point of what I have listed above that would be approved by some idealist philosopher. All German classical idealists considered empirical knowledge and natural science as an inferior kind of knowledge, while they appreciated the pure conceptual knowledge of philosophy. Moreover, the contrast between idealism and science has been particularly strong and harmful in Italy. Here, Benedetto Croce's authority, who once defined the scientific theories as "kitchen recipes", excluded Italian philosophy from international debate for decades. For example, in his lifetime, Giuseppe Peano had more reputation abroad than in Italy.

The distinction between two possible kinds of monism, materialism and idealism, can also be understood with the issue of the naturalization of the mental. In fact, once the physical states have been identified with the mental ones, we still have to find out if mental phenomena are physical phenomena or the way round. The decision does not matter (it would be, surely, trivial) if it consisted only, so to speak, in changing sign to phenomena (<<even physicists, in recent times, have given less consideration to the matter: have moved to imponderable matters, like heat, light, etc.>> Hegel, *Encyclopedia of philosophical sciences*, *Anmerkung* to par. 389). If physical phenomena "are attracted" by mental ones or *vice versa*, involves a radical change in the task and value of empirical science (and, consequently, of philosophy too).

Naturalizing the mind is not the same as making nature mental (<<but vital matter [...] lacks [...] every other determined being, so that it cannot be placed with material things>> Hegel, *ibid.*). If the mental is a natural phenomenon, and nobody has yet demonstrated that it is not, then science is the obvious candidate to explain it: this scientific task is unacceptable for any idealist.

Among the strongest points in favor of idealism there is the fact that we can characterize reality only through the processes of our mind. But followers of realism think that the question we ask about reality (expression used by Galilei to define experiment) are answered by reality itself. I do not think we can obtain idealism from any thesis that states any form of dependence of the observed facts from the observer, because, no matter how few, the contribution of the facts observed will remain, while for idealism this contribution is null.

Hutto considers Bradley's thesis according to which <<True is Entire>> to be the strongest point of idealism. This thesis is, as well known, a Hegelian thesis. Hutto's observations are typically Hegelian when he states that sciences give only partial truth because sciences take care only of partial aspects of reality (Hegel's consideration comes from the fact that sciences use the intellect rather than reason). The reconstruction of the totality is not possible for the sciences. The total of the partial truths are the Truth, the Absolute Truth, and, for Hegel, the Absolute (i.e. the totality of the finite). Hutto accepts these idealistic claims but rejects the consequences (the ones I have mentioned above) valuing science against traditional idealists' claims. If such an operation is possible I do not know, I have already expressed my doubts on the subject. But the readers of the book can have different opinions and I am ready to change mine. The point is this: let us admit, as Hutto seems to propose, that it is possible to separate <<what is alive from what is dead >>(Croce) in idealism. So, let us admit that idealism is a metaphysical position more coherent with modern science and with epistemology (because of the data of observation are laden with theory) than physicalism. Why should we agree to the thesis that the <<True is the Entire>>? Why should we have to believe in absolute truth and rehabilitate metaphysics? (The history of scientific and philosophical thought of 19th and 20th centuries has demonstrated the uselessness of searching for Absolute Truth).

There are two kinds of reductionism: the methodological one and the ontological one. The former implies the latter, but not vice versa. According to ontological reductionism, real entities are only physical entities; moreover, according to methodological reductionism there is a fundamental science (physics) which will comprehend all possible physical entities. So it is possible to think that reality is made only of physical entities but it is organized on different levels which cannot be methodologically reduced. Therefore, also if it is possible to reduce chemistry to physics or biology to physics, it might be the case that theories belonging to levels that are "too distant" cannot be reduced.

The armies that engaged in the battle of Waterloo were made of physical entities - human beings with mental states and brain states - but it seems impossible to describe the historical event <<the battle of Waterloo>> in the terms of brain states of the single soldier. Perhaps it could also be impossible to reduce mental states to brain states (as methodological reductionism requires), but that does not mean no physical events exist too (ontological reductionism). Therefore an absolute vision of the truth could be possible only in one of the hierarchical levels of reality. If only one "locally absolute" vision was available, we would be satisfied.

Paraphrasing Crane and Mellor who claimed that nobody will not speak about physicalism after their assertions, I think philosophers should stop dealing with the mind-body problem: if there were a philosophical answer to that problem we would have (from Plato to nowadays) already found it. If there is an answer, it will come from empirical investigation, otherwise there is no answer (or perhaps no problem).

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[Reply](#)

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